

THE IMPACT OF CRITICAL READING SKILLS TO POSTGRADUATE STUDENTS' ACADEMIC SUCCESS

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The increasing demand for postgraduate education, which is one of the innovative essence of any sphere of advancement, has increased so far, and the ability of doing research is one of the requirements of it, namely critical reading skills. The purpose of the following literature review is to evaluate the definition of critical reading by various researchers, critical reading skills explicitly, its impact on postgraduates' academic success, the challenges of carried out research and their results, controversial ideas of researchers and suggestions to improve critical reading for graduate students. Assessing postgraduate students' understanding of their critical reading skills is very crucial because obtaining a considerable amount of data is needed for the accomplishment of research. According to Arslan (2022) various kinds of reading are existed on the basis of the aim and requirement of the person from the reading methodology. There are various kinds of reading ; reading loudly, quietly, skimming, assuming and critical reading. Among them the critical reading is the one, which in academic achievement possesses a vital role.

The term of critical reading will be defined before giving explanation and how it refers to the academic concept of postgraduate students. The term critical reading is making logical analysis, evaluation, synthesizing, argumentum in reading of what is read. While surveying the topic, it was observed that critical reading was studied by a number of researchers. According to Cervetti, Pardales, and Damico (2001) critical reading is the method of assessing the integrity information and of establishing a judgment about it. Wallace (2003) claims that critical reading can be approached by analyzing text rather than general reading (p. 44), he also points out that the aim of the critical reading is to acquire an ample comprehension of the real content of the text, which is irrefutable part of the research point. He means that in general reading it is not important questioning, but in critical reading it is. Critical reading contrasts from reading skeptic, so according to Wheeler (2007), a critical reader attempts to synthesize ideas rather than refute. By this he means that a critical reader analyses and evaluates essential details. Milan (1995) noted that being critical requires detailed examination, pragmatism and rational capacities (p. 218), the research cites that analytical syntheses of the context are required in critical reading. Also, in accordance with Freire

(2005)critical reading should indeed be approached as a method of equally like understanding the word and reciting the world (p. 31). By this statement he meant that the reader of the text is actually the second author. Complying with this idea Salvatori and Donahue (2005) have claimed that the main positive issue of being co-authors gives the responsibility for the interpreted meaning of the text details.

The number of research explanations for the effect of critical reading skills to postgraduates are provided. In accordance with Wallase and Wray (2021) critical reading skills are accepted as the main component at the postgraduate level. Khalil (2019) mentioned that critical reading is important for graduate level students since it supports them with available evidences, necessary data for their survey paper. Kim(2020) argues that skilled readers frequently pass exams successfully compared to unskilled students, because critical readers adopt a variety of effective reading techniques. Based on the researchers **Ferdous** and Mahmuda (2022) **the strategies of critical reading skills are:** 1) Evaluating; 2) Interpreting 3) Replying; 4)Synthesizing; 5)Examining 5) Re-reading. However, according to Arıçı (2008) critical reading is as a “reading tool“ and includes separating parts, comprising the idea and using effective techniques of the context, identifying the goal and utilizing them towards the topic, locate primary ideas of text, key features, statements, paragraphs; create cause-effect connection between paragraphs; search and discover the correlation with each other ; criticize non-hidden ideas ; explore narrated techniques by the writer.

Critical reading is an important ability, which ought to be taught elaborately during the academic years. Enhancing critical reading abilities is essential for success in the academic world and critical reading levels proved to have considerable positive effect on other academic skills like listening and watching skills. Numerous books and scholar articles were written about the importance of critical reading in the education process. (Wallace and Wray (2011), Mikelson (2018)) The primary purpose of critical reading in education is its powerful impact on students’ critical thinking. In this regard, it is stated that the primary aim of modern various educational system is to improve the critical reading skills in academic performance and methods, namely postgraduate levels (Shamida, Siddhu and Nawi(2021). The inadequate language and research abilities of postgraduate students have been identified among the many other contributing factors in this regard, the study on postgraduate students critical reading in the base of a Reading test paper was carried out with 50 students from a non-governmental Malaysian university and it revealed that students were sure about their own ability rather than critical reading skills, results demonstrated that creative strategies are needed in order to complete graduation on time. Postgraduate students

are required to have a solid working understanding of the topic, be able to comprehend academic context, and be able to write their theses with a quality that is acceptable. Wang (2009) discovered that in order to comprehend the essence of a text, a learner needs proficient reading abilities to produce implicit primary concepts.

Based on the book of Wallace and Wray (2011) point out that ability to read the text critically is determining the level of the justification of the authors in the text which they provide, they state also that enabling critical reading skills help academic learners to sort relevant information by evaluating its argument containing conclusion from a wide range of literature which is accessible in advanced internet resources. Kurland (2000) asserted that it is not just attentive reading, but a critical reader should assess and examine the text's supporting evidence. He added that a critical reader should be aware of what to look for and how to process what they discover from the text. The researchers Edman(2008); Ennis(2018); Hervás & Miralles(2006); Huijie(2010); Wade (2008) cited the close association of the capacity to read analytically, academic accomplishment, and the demand for thinking critically. Baba & Affendi (2020) claimed that reading is a necessary ability for graduate studies because it enables students to comprehend their research topics on a deeper level. Wallace and Wray (2021) stated that one of the main principles of postgraduate studies is the development of critical reading skills. Khalil (2019) believed that critical reading is crucial for postgraduates so it enables them to develop persuasive arguments or find relevant data for their research projects. If students are not competent in questioning the arguments, they get challenges doing their research work. Students that are excellent in critical reading skills will also be better able to communicate their opinions and points of view. Moreover, students should devour a great deal of academic articles to sort the essential information on their thesis, reading comprehension improves students' academic performance as well as non-cognitive academic outcomes like agency, persistence, and delight, according to Garcia-Navarrete, Sax & Levine (2012); Guthrie & Klauda (2014); McLaughlin & Rasinski (2015). Nevertheless, Wallas (2003) mentioned that, albeit mentioning the significance of critical reading, its seriousness has not been taken into consideration. Notwithstanding this approach, study shows that several higher education students have difficulty with reading materials of a complex nature efficiently. The effectiveness of the instructional structure examined by questioning students according to Douglas (2016), Holschuh & Paulson (2013), Manarin (2016) and Allen (2011) claimed that techniques such as scanning, defining the terms based on context, underlining and synthesizing main ideas used by pedagogies explain as a means of accomplishing goals restricting learners to get experience from the text (p.

99). Consequently, students believe that it is because of reading deficiency not knowing the given technique incompetency, stated Salvatori & Donahue(2005); Smith(2012). According to Hudson (2007) the capability to read critically and interpret the data are vital for high school students due to the fact that they can get detailed information by posing a question, students who are introduced to critical reading techniques properly will be able to recognize and synthesize main ideas or compare texts critically and achieve better results.

There are a number of reasons why critical reading impacts on academic purposes have been studied in the present literature review. Firstly, many students misunderstand the difficulties of completing postgraduate courses, according to Dreyer and Nel (2003). With having inefficient critical reading skills their academic performance seems challenging for them. Another point of view is as Khodary and Abdallah's (2014) research describes, the students face inadequacy in concluding, determining cause and consequences connections, analyzing justifications while studying. Low academic literacy and research capabilities in accordance with Sidhu, Kaur, Fook, and Yunus (2013) distracting students from academic success. Çam (2006) based on his founding in Turkish classes (the research was done with 800 (280 female-420 male)students of Sivas city center in the autumn term of 2021-2022) stated that critical thinking and critical reading skills grow educational excellence.

In this point of view some suggestions can be listed in order to improve critical reading.

Since critical reading can be taught and trained, it is essential to teach critical reading skills to students at every level of the education process. Background knowledge of critical reading from schools can be one of the opportunities. Critical reading skills can be improved by starting reading habits especially at schools. Critical reading techniques and materials should be prepared and implemented in primary, secondary and high schools, in accordance with Ozensoy (2020). Innovative approach is suggested in teaching critical reading skills. Students should improve critical thinking abilities, as it is interrelated to analytical reading skills. Fleming and Weber (1980) highlighted the importance of creating the instructional sources, tactics, and strategies to cultivate critical reading abilities of students. Another contributing issue can be turning inefficient teaching of critical reading strategies into effective. Five critical important critical questions are listed by Weber (year) in a list of recommendations such as ; - What is the reason I am reading this? - What is the purpose of authoring this? - What is the connection between my focused topic and authors' provided data? How reliable are authors statements? - What kind of conclusion can I get from it? Carr (1988) cited that reading magazines, papers, television and radios in the class are important in

order to improve critical reading skills. Manarin (2015) noted that the reader should work on the content of the text by re-reading compared to develop a definite perception.

In conclusion, having evaluated the study of the relationship between critical reading and academic attainment, it can be concluded that critical reading is one of the crucial skills for accomplishing academic level. Critical reading skills should be accepted as a main skill for academics and needs to be improved by working collaboratively with teachers and studied research work demonstrates the importance of developing critical reading skills for postgraduate students. Students need effective strategies, techniques, materials of critical reading from their instructors towards the aim of improvement. The advantages of improving critical reading skills for graduate students are: 1) students can easily choose relevant articles by distinguishing from reliable and unreliable sources ; 2) they can enhance reading and writing skills by highly suggested strategies. 3) Students should improve reading habits in order to move to critical reading skills which lead to successful accomplishment of their chosen researches.

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